

A Qualitative Study of How Youth Engage with News Aggregator Apps

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We live in an "information age" where news can be disseminated with the aid of technology. In India, the availability of cheap data packs, greater internet penetration and availability of affordable smartphones has helped audiences access and download mobile apps, including news aggregator apps. News aggregation in the digital space started with news aggregator websites and evolved into news aggregator apps. Millennial and Generation Z (Gen Z) audiences are known to quickly adapt to new technology. Using qualitative methods, we study the audience engagement of Indian youth (age group 18 to 35) living in tier 1 and II cities, in terms of how they engage with three news aggregator apps, features that appeal to them, and whether they experience information overload. The findings indicate that the audience is significantly engaged with news aggregator apps, value specific features, and have devised strategies to cope with the volume of information.

Introduction

1.1. News and its dissemination

News is disseminated through mediums like newspapers, magazines, television channels, websites and news applications. News organizations gain advertising/subscription revenue from websites and hence, have been at the forefront of digital news generation. Most prominent media organisations in India also have news apps for the mobile phone.

The challenge for media organisations is to appeal to the under-35 age group, who are tech-savvy.

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1.2. The information age

Modern society is described as an "information age" or a time when information is akin to a commodity, can be quickly disseminated and is available through the use of computer technology (Merriam-Webster).

The term New Media is used to describe the emergence of digital communication technologies (Humida, 2015).

The India Digital News Report (2019) shows that India is a mobile-first market, with 68% of respondents identifying smartphones as their main device for accessing online news and 31% saying they only use mobile devices for accessing online news.

1.3. News aggregators

A news aggregator is an online platform or software device that collects news stories as the information is published and organises the information in a specific manner (Pallardy & Hanff, 2016).

News aggregators originally consisted of websites that grouped information from various sources to present them on a single platform. With technological advancement, there emerged smartphone apps. The aggregation can be manual or automated with the help of algorithms and Artificial Intelligence (AI).

In India, the period from 2010 onwards saw the launch of apps like Inshorts (2013) and Dailyhunt (2010). Google News' aggregator app, which is available globally, was launched in 2006.

1.4. News aggregators and social media connect

News aggregator apps let users share content on social media. One of the strengths of news aggregators lies in their incorporation of the social media flow into content consumption (Terron & Castellet, 2013).

1.5. Role of algorithms

Social media, news websites, and news aggregator apps try to understand the usage pattern with the help of algorithms that inform them of aspects contributing to engagement or hindering usage.

1.6. Aggregation as a point of contention

Aggregation occupies a grey zone in journalism, as the work does not involve original content creation.

Some critics consider it akin to copyright infringement. In many cases, there is no monetary arrangement or licensing for use of information. Rupert Murdoch, chairman of News Corp., equated aggregation of media content to stealing (Murdoch, 2009).

There have been lawsuits against news aggregators globally to regulate the usage of content. It remains a contentious matter based on the rules of the country where the news aggregator operates.

The best practices followed by news aggregator companies to reduce legal risk are to reproduce only portions of headlines/articles, not reproducing all articles from a single source, prominently identifying/linking to the source of the article, and providing context for the material used (Isbell, 2010).

1.7. Media saturation and news

News is constantly streaming via new media platforms such as social media and podcasts (Lee et al., 2016).

Bawden and Robinson (2009) define the term Information Overload (IO) to be a situation where the efficiency of an individual in using information is hampered by the amount of relevant information available. It may be accompanied by feelings of anxiety, powerlessness, exhaustion and de-sensitisation to news.

1.8. Popular news aggregator apps in India

The top 3 top news aggregator apps in India as per the rankings of global app intelligence agency App Annie are Inshorts, Dailyhunt, and Google News. We have focused on these apps for our study.

1.8.1. Inshorts

Inshorts displays textual content (in 60 words) of the latest events happening around the country and the world on a mobile phone. Active users range in the age group of 20-30 years. Their feed is tailored to a person's reading choice.

1.8.2. Dailyhunt

One of the older news aggregator apps in India, Dailyhunt is available in multiple languages. The app also lets you monitor and follow Twitter feeds. The comment option given is a distinct feature.

1.8.3. Google News

Google News is a global news aggregator and has been developed by technology giant Google. The site was conceptualised by Google employee Krishna Bharat. It is available in more than a dozen languages. A new version launched in 2018 applies AI and machine learning to customise content. It is non-commercial and does not showcase any advertisement.

Theoretical framework

The following communication theories have been used for the study:

2.1. Uses and gratification theory

This theory was proposed by Elihu Katz and Jay Blumler (1974) and helps us understand why audiences actively seek out certain media content for gratification.

2.2. Agenda setting theory

This theory proposed by Maxwell McCombs and Donald Shaw (1968) states that media filters and determines what issues are regarded as important in society. Gatekeeping is a process whereby media organisations decide whether to carry a particular news story or not.

2.3. Media convergence theory

The Media convergence theory by Henry Jenkins (2006) states that with the advent of news communication technologies, mass mediums combine and transform into one medium.

2.4. Marshall McLuhan's medium theory

Marshall McLuhan's Medium Theory (1964) states that new forms of media transform our experience of ourselves and our society and, in essence, the medium is the message. Through interconnected networks, the world is transformed into a "global village".

Research methodology

3.1. Aim

To study audience engagement with news aggregator apps among youth in terms of information consumption.

3.2. Research questions

RQ1 Which are the features and functionality that make a particular news aggregator app appeal to the youth audience?

RQ2 How do youth engage with news aggregator apps in terms of information consumption?

RQ3 Do news aggregator apps cause optimal information consumption among youth?

3.3. Hypothesis

H1 English news aggregator apps have significant audience engagement with youth.

H0 English news aggregator apps do not have significant audience engagement with youth.

3.4. Research design

To find the answers to the research questions and test the hypothesis, a qualitative approach and research design was used to collect data.

In qualitative research, a detailed analysis of a relatively small sample is used to find answers to questions like "why" and "how" a phenomenon occurs. This method is usually used to understand/describe motives, behaviours and perceptions that may be difficult to grasp through quantitative methods.

Reliability and validity of the findings are established in the qualitative paradigm through elements like trustworthiness, rigour and quality of the data (Golafshani, 2003). We have ensured that the methods have been described in detail, the research questions are clear, the theoretical framework is explained in depth and linked to the study (Saldana, 2021).

3.5. Method

This study was conducted using qualitative methods of Focus Group Discussions, Content Analysis, and In-depth Interviews.

Focus group discussions were conducted with 30 participants who belong to the age group of 18 to 35. We divided them into groups of five participants and asked them questions from a structured questionnaire. The responses were recorded on Zoom.

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In-depth interviews were conducted with five industry persons who have either founded or worked in news aggregator apps. Along with this, we did a content analysis of three highly ranked news aggregator apps.

Data was analyzed by applying inductive methods such as thematic analysis, latent and manifest content analysis, and constant comparison technique whereby the researcher recorded, transcribed, analysed the transcript and grouped data according to categories, codes and themes.

The sample populations for the discussion are Gen Z and millennial youth living in tier 1 and 2 cities. We applied snowball sampling to select the participants. The sample population is homogenous and consists of working professionals and students.

3.6. Results and discussion

The data collected from the focus group discussion was analyzed and the findings were as follows:

A majority of participants have been using news aggregator apps for more than two years and spend less than half an hour a day on news aggregator apps. News aggregator apps are the main source of news for a majority of respondents, while social media comes a close second.

Image 1: Pros of news aggregator apps

Most of the respondents used the app Inshorts followed by those who used Inshorts and Google News, and those who used Google News and Dailyhunt. Some respondents used all three apps.

When the respondents were asked about the features they liked in news aggregator apps, the most common response was that news is given concisely (13), followed by news being simple to understand (10). Other important factors were that news is constantly available, there is access to free news, and news from multiple sources can be read on one platform (9 respondents each).

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Image 2: Cons of news aggregator apps

In terms of cons, a majority of respondents consider the constant notifications (11) to be a deterrent. It is followed by limited information given by the medium (9), and "bombarding of ads" (8).

Image 3: Features of news aggregator apps

For most of the participants, the primary factor they consider is the headline, text, image and font used by the news aggregator (26). It is followed by navigability and ease of use, and story selection (20 each).

From the thematic analysis, the findings show that users engage with these apps by sharing snippets of information, customising the app to their preference, finding ways to tackle information saturation, verifying the content before sending it, and recalling information they read.

Notifications are both a pro and con for users. Some recipients experience Information Overload from it and uninstall the app. Most of the participants could recall the stories they read, which shows optimal information consumption. Most users are unwilling to pay to avoid ads.

From the interviews conducted, it is evident that youth is an important demographic group for news aggregator apps. Apps are trying to offer features that help users customise the app and feel less stressed out by reading news.

Many apps use a mix of manual and algorithm-based newsgathering, which shows that gatekeeping (in terms of content selection and verification) as well as news writing are preferably done by people rather than machines. Organisations do additional processes for verification of content and to ensure diversity of sources.

Most of the organisations use news as a public domain good and access it from websites and repackage it. There are very few who have tie-ups for use of content.

Content analysis showed that the news selection on all the three apps is a mixture of AI as well as manual selection. Inshorts manages to balance both manual and AI-based aggregation by getting their team of editors to rewrite the content (headlines and text) and also letting the algorithm track user preference.

Among the apps we studied, Dailyhunt had similarities to social media apps in terms of certain features. Google News made it easy to send feedback and had the least number of notifications.

Conclusion

Youth is an important demographic for news aggregator apps. Interviews with industry persons show that news aggregator app companies are trying to innovate with their features and functionality to keep users engaged.

The focus group discussions highlighted features that are important to the youth demographic including the ability to get concise news without any cost. They engage with the app by sharing information and taking the effort to verify content by going to the link. Some users have found ways to deal with the deluge of notifications through custom settings.

Content analysis has helped us understand the similarities and differences between the three apps. Users looking for certain features opt for the apps based on the feature and functionality it offers.

As a result of this study, certain recommendations have emerged that news aggregator apps can improve upon. It includes focusing on generating easy-to-read original content as well as offering analysis and localised content. There needs to be easier access to the section/button to report content and give feedback.

Limitations

- 1) This study is restricted to usage of English language news aggregator apps.
- 2) The study focuses on youth living in Mumbai, Pune, Jaipur, Ahmedabad and Kanpur. A majority of respondents are from Mumbai.
- 3) The apps that have been selected for content analysis are available for download on Android. The researcher doesn't have access to iOS apps.

Future scope of study

The scope of the research can be extended to cover regional language news aggregators. The usage of news aggregator apps across other age groups would also yield important data. Since this study was done on a small sample size, a survey study may be done to generate quantifiable data.

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